

DataTools4Heart MS16 Qualitative Evaluation Questionnaire

Baseline System

Purpose of the questionnaire. This questionnaire is intended to collect structured qualitative feedback on the Named Entity Recognition system developed within MS16. The evaluation focuses on the system output for the recognition and labelling of clinically relevant entities, including diseases, symptoms, procedures and medications.

The information collected through this form will support the analysis of system performance, the identification of common error patterns, the documentation of model behaviour, and the definition of future improvements for clinical NLP within the DataTools4Heart project.

Important. Please complete this questionnaire only if you have tested or explored the demo/system output. This questionnaire refers specifically to the **Baseline system**.

* Required question

Evaluator Information

Q1. Email *: _____

Q2. First name *: _____

Q3. Last name *: _____

Q4. Name of organisation, institution or company *

Select all that apply.

- Vall d'Hebron Hospital Research Institute
- Amsterdam University Medical Centre
- University Medical Center Utrecht
- Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS
- University College London
- Region Stockholm
- International Clinical Research Center
- Bucharest Emergency Clinical Hospital
- European Society of Cardiology
- Barcelona Supercomputing Center
- Other: _____

Q5. Native language(s) *

Select all that apply.

- English
- Spanish
- Dutch
- Italian
- Czech
- Swedish
- Romanian
- Catalan
- German
- French
- Greek
- Other: _____

Q6. Language evaluated *

Select one option only.

- English
- Spanish
- Dutch
- Italian
- Czech
- Swedish
- Romanian

Q7. Expertise/background *

Select all that apply.

- Clinical or healthcare professional
- Technical expert or engineer
- Other: _____

General System Performance

Q8. How well do you think the tested automatic system for recognizing clinical entities performed? *

Clinical entities include diseases, symptoms, procedures and medications. Select all that apply.

- Very well
- Well, with some minor errors
- Well, but I found errors
- Requires significant improvements
- Did not work very well, with many errors
- Very bad results; it did not recognize the clinical entities

Q9. How well do you think the tested automatic system performed for labelling disease mentions? *

Select all that apply.

- Very well
- Well, with some minor errors
- Well, but I found errors
- Requires significant improvements
- Did not work very well, with many errors
- Very bad results; it did not recognize the clinical entities

Q10. How well do you think the tested automatic system performed for labelling symptom mentions? *

Select all that apply.

- Very well
- Well, with some minor errors
- Well, but I found errors
- Requires significant improvements
- Did not work very well, with many errors
- Very bad results; it did not recognize the clinical entities

Q11. How well do you think the tested automatic system performed for labelling *procedure* mentions? *

Select all that apply.

- Very well
- Well, with some minor errors
- Well, but I found errors
- Requires significant improvements
- Did not work very well, with many errors
- Very bad results; it did not recognize the clinical entities

Q12. How well do you think the tested automatic system performed for labelling *medication* mentions? *

Select all that apply.

- Very well
- Well, with some minor errors
- Well, but I found errors
- Requires significant improvements
- Did not work very well, with many errors
- Very bad results; it did not recognize the clinical entities

Q13. Do you think that the automatic detection/extraction of these clinical entities is useful? *

Select one option only.

- Very useful
- Useful
- Average degree of usefulness
- Limited degree of usefulness
- Not useful at all

Qualitative Feedback

Q14. Could you provide short feedback on your impressions of what worked well when examining the generated results?

Q15. Could you provide short feedback on your impressions of some of the errors you observed and provide some examples?

Observed Error Types

Q16. **Boundary Errors / Span Errors**

Only select those that you actually observed when testing the system. Select all that apply.

Partial mention / incomplete span. Only part of the entity is tagged. Example: “diabetes mellitus” tagged instead of “diabetes mellitus type 2”.

Over-extended span. Extra tokens are included in the entity. Example: “observed diabetes mellitus” tagged when only “diabetes mellitus” should be labelled.

Split entity / segmentation. A single entity is split into multiple mentions. Example: “intermittent” and “fever” tagged separately instead of “intermittent fever”.

Merged entities. Two separate entities are incorrectly combined into one span. Example: “aspirin ibuprofen” tagged as a single entity.

Other: _____

Q17. **Type / Label Errors**

Only select those that you actually observed when testing the system. Select all that apply.

Wrong entity type / misclassification. Correct span, wrong label. Example: “Valsartan” tagged as DISEASE instead of MEDICATION.

Confusion between related types. Common in domain-specific settings, for example symptom vs. disease.

Other: _____

Q18. Missing Entities / False Negatives

Only select those that you actually observed when testing the system. Select all that apply.

- Complete omission.** The entity is not detected at all.
- Missed nested entity.** A valid entity inside a longer span is not identified separately, when nested NER is expected.
- Other: _____

Q19. Spurious Entities / False Positives

Only select those that you actually observed when testing the system. Select all that apply.

- Hallucinated entity.** A non-entity phrase is incorrectly tagged as an entity.
- Contextually incorrect tagging.** A word that can be an entity in some contexts is incorrectly tagged in another. Example: “CVD” tagged as DISEASE if it corresponds to “Cardiovascular Disease”, but not if it corresponds to “Central Venous Delivery”.
- Other: _____

Q20. Ambiguity and Context Errors

Only select those that you actually observed when testing the system. Select all that apply.

- Abbreviation resolution error.** Misclassification or failure to detect abbreviated entities. Example: “MS” incorrectly tagged due to ambiguity, such as multiple sclerosis vs. mitral stenosis.
- Coreference-related inconsistency.** The same entity is referred to differently but is not consistently recognized.
- Other: _____

Q21. Formatting and Tokenization Errors

Only select those that you actually observed when testing the system. Select all that apply.

- Tokenization mismatch.** Entity boundaries are affected by punctuation or special characters. Example: punctuation marks included in the mention, “heart failure.” tagged instead of “heart failure”.
- Hyphenation or compound handling error.** Example: “COVID-19 related” improperly split or partially tagged.
- Other: _____

Q22. Domain-Specific Errors, if applicable

Only select those that you actually observed when testing the system. Select all that apply.

Terminology variation errors. Synonyms or multiple mentions of the same entity are not consistently recognized.

Rare or emerging term failure. New terminology or clinical jargon is not detected.

Numerical qualifier omission. Modifiers such as stage, grade, type or dosage are not included in the entity span.

Other: _____

Q23. Are there any other comments, feedback or observations you would like to provide?

Overall Ratings**Q24. Give an overall rating of the complete output from 0 to 10. ***

Select one option only, where 0 indicates the lowest rating and 10 the highest rating.

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Q25. Give an overall rating of the DISEASE label output from 0 to 10. *

Select one option only, where 0 indicates the lowest rating and 10 the highest rating.

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Q26. Give an overall rating of the SYMPTOM label output from 0 to 10. *

Select one option only, where 0 indicates the lowest rating and 10 the highest rating.

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Q27. Give an overall rating of the PROCEDURE label output from 0 to 10. *

Select one option only, where 0 indicates the lowest rating and 10 the highest rating.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>										

Q28. Give an overall rating of the MEDICATION label output from 0 to 10. *

Select one option only, where 0 indicates the lowest rating and 10 the highest rating.

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>										